

GROUP CONTRACT: A BOOST FOR COMMITMENT AND EFFECTIVENESS IN COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

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Abstract: *This article examines the implementation of the group contract as a pedagogical tool supporting the collaborative teaching-learning methodology applied in the Organizational Management course, integrated into various engineering programs. The group contract was designed to formalize collaboration norms, clarify expectations, and foster accountability and commitment among students in group work. Its structure includes components such as group identification, communication norms, outcome expectations, behavioral guidelines, and strategies for effective teamwork. The implementation process involves initial activities of individual reflection and group discussion, followed by the creation and formalization of the contract, signed by all group members. Throughout the semester, periodic reviews allow for adjustments to norms and the addressing of emerging challenges, contributing to a more efficient collaborative dynamic. The results highlight that the group contract enhances group cohesion, improves communication, and promotes a more balanced division of tasks, reinforcing essential interpersonal skills for both academic and professional contexts. This study underscores the importance of the group contract as a key support tool in collaborative learning methodologies.*

Keywords: *Active methodologies; Team-Based Learning (TBL); Collaborative learning; Group work; Group contract*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, teamwork is one of the most widely used strategies in organizations (Pertegal-Felices, Fuster-Guilló, Rico-Soliveres, Azorín-López, & Jimeno-Morenilla, 2019), because it promotes efficiency, innovation, and adaptability, qualities that are essential in the increasingly dynamic and competitive environments in which organizations operate (Salas, Shuffler, Thayer, Bedwell, & Lazzara, 2015). Through teamwork, individuals share knowledge, leverage complementary skills, and enhance the development of more effective solutions compared to those achieved individually (Salas et al., 2015).

In higher education, the use of active methodologies in the teaching-learning process, which includes collaborative work, has proven particularly effective in preparing students for these challenges. It enables them to develop essential skills such as communication, professionalism, conflict management, and knowledge acquisition through sharing. (Brannen et al., 2021; Cagliesi & Ghanei, 2022; Zalewski & Brudvig, 2022).

In the academic setting, the term "team" is often replaced by "group," with group work widely recognized as a task that can be both rewarding and dissatisfying. Group work is an experience whose benefits are well-documented but can also bring frustrations; the phrase "grin and bear it" (Zalewski & Brudvig, 2022), is often used to encapsulate the inherent difficulties and tensions of this process. Being part of an ineffective or dysfunctional group

can hinder students' learning and outcomes, leading to feelings of frustration and resentment (Oakley, Felder, Brent, & Elhajj, 2004).

As a result, it is essential for those responsible for the teaching-learning process to play an active role in creating conditions conducive to effective group work. To foster productive collaborative work, it is crucial to introduce tools and practices that promote a balanced distribution of responsibilities, support the management of expectations, and encourage accountability among group members (Clark, Merrick, Styron, & Dolowitz, 2021).

In this context, the concept of the group contract emerges as a valuable tool, as it allows for the formalization of each student's commitment to the group and establishes the foundation for equitable collaboration among all group members (Brannen et al., 2021). This commitment, discussed, written, and agreed upon by all members, creates a foundation of trust and cooperation, enabling each member to feel responsible and invested in the collective success (Clinton & Smith, 2009).

Thus, it is a pedagogical tool that supports the development of group work. When implemented at the beginning of academic activities, it enables the instructor to better manage students' expectations and proactively address potential issues, such as inequalities in participation, thereby fostering a more harmonious and productive collaborative environment (Pertegal-Felices et al., 2019).

This article aims to explore the implementation and role of the group contract in the context of collaborative learning, highlighting its advantages in group performance and the promotion of academic success. Based on a critical analysis supported by recent studies and a practical implementation case, the objective is to demonstrate how this tool contributes to the enhancement of the collaborative approach in the teaching-learning process.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The implementation of group contracts was carried out in the Organizational Management course across various engineering programs, involving first- and third-year students. These courses employed the collaborative learning methodology based on Team-Based Learning (TBL) (Rodrigues & Sousa, 2024), where tools to promote effective group functioning are particularly important, as TBL requires active collaboration and a strong sense of shared responsibility among group members.

At the beginning of each course edition, students were given a detailed explanation of how TBL classes operate, with an emphasis on the advantages of this method in the teaching-learning process. Subsequently, the group contract was introduced. Including the completion of the group contract in the lesson plan and ensuring sufficient time for its execution reinforces the importance of this activity.

At the start of the activity, instructors encouraged students to reflect on past group work experiences, identifying successes, challenges, and areas for improvement. Following this reflection, each student shared their insights with their group members. This sharing served as a starting point for defining the norms that would guide the group's collaboration. Additionally, students were informed that the contract would remain confidential among group members, fostering an environment conducive to the open expression of ideas and concerns.

The group contract provided to students is composed of five sections: Group Identification, Group Communication, Outcome Expectations, Group Behavior, and Effective Group Work, concluding with the signatures of all group members. This document was designed in accordance with recommendations from the literature (Brannen et al., 2021; Clinton & Smith, 2009; George Brown University, n.d.; Oakley et al., 2004; University of Newcastle, n.d.; University of Waterloo, n.d.)

Midway through each semester, instructors conduct a follow-up session in which students are invited to revisit their group contract, reflect on the progress made, and adjust the agreed terms if necessary to maintain cohesion and effectiveness in collaborative work. This practice of continuous review reinforces members' commitment to the agreed responsibilities and helps consolidate group collaboration (Hesterman, 2016).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion of the implementation of the group contract in the Organizational Management courses are presented according to the main components of the contract: Group Identification, Group Communication, Outcome Expectations, Group Behavior, and Effective Group Work. The document supporting the group contract includes the following statement, which students are invited to reflect upon: "Group work only happens when group members cooperate and utilize their individual skills to achieve common goals."

The initial component of the group contract is the clear identification of each group member within the institutional context (Figure 1).

Group name:		
Group members	Name	Student number

Figure 1. Identification of group members.

In addition to completing the document, students were encouraged to share a bit about themselves with their peers. This activity aimed to foster the creation of bonds among students and help establish a foundation of mutual trust, which is essential for collaborative work. This practice enhances closeness among students, particularly in groups where members do not already know one another.

The next section of the contract addresses the communication process among group members (Figure 2).

Communication tools			
Group meetings (day, time, location)			
Group members' contacts	Name	Phone number	Email

Figure 2. Group communication.

Before defining their communication methods, students reflected on the following text: the ability to express opinions and understand others' perspectives is essential for effective group communication. All members should feel comfortable sharing ideas and feelings, fostering open and honest exchange. Active listening is equally critical, allowing each member to listen attentively and provide constructive feedback. Furthermore, respectful communication—both verbal and non-verbal—that considers cultural and personal differences contributes to group cohesion and success.

Defining communication tools is essential to ensuring clear and effective interaction. The groups established rules regarding the frequency of meetings and the communication methods (such as email, messaging groups, and collaborative platforms), which facilitated task coordination and information sharing. This aspect is particularly relevant during the mid-semester follow-up, where groups can adjust communication mechanisms if the process reveals shortcomings.

The next section is dedicated to outcome expectations and aims to allow group members to align their goals and objectives from the outset (Figure 3).

		Grade expectation
Group members		
Group		

Figure 3. Outcome expectations.

Students were guided to share their expectations regarding the final grade for the group project and to reach a consensus on a target grade. Prior to this, they were asked to reflect on the following questions: To ensure the group works effectively, members must share the same goals: "Is each member committed to working as needed to achieve the grade agreed upon by the group? If some group members only aim to pass the course while others aspire to achieve high grades, how do you think the group will function?"

At this stage, it may be necessary to revise the group composition if students' expectations are not aligned. This adjustment helps prevent the development of conflicts and avoids the persistence of dysfunctional groups that could face more serious issues in the future.

The next section focuses on the behavior of each member in group work (Figure 4). Its objective is to promote an environment of respect and collaboration by defining each member's expectations regarding their peers' conduct and clarifying behaviors that could generate tensions.

Group member	General expectation	Specific expectation

Figure 4. Group member behavior.

Students reflected on the behaviors required to work effectively as a group. For example: "communicating with one another in a timely manner, being punctual for meetings and classes, meeting task deadlines, being polite and respectful to peers, etc." Each group member should include in the table their expectations regarding the behavior (both general and specific) of the group members. For instance: "I expect everyone to be punctual (general), arriving at classes and meetings on time (specific)."

The mid-semester review can be particularly beneficial for this section, allowing groups to reflect on behavioral issues that create a negative environment and to define solutions to improve group dynamics.

The final section, effective group work, encourages reflection on each member’s strengths and weaknesses (Figure 5).

Group member	Strengths

Group member	Weaknesses
	(Ctrl) ▾

Figure 5. Effective group work.

A list of key competencies essential for effective group work (leadership, organization, planning, etc.) was provided, along with an explanation of each. It was further explained that each competency could represent either a strength or a weakness for individual students. Concrete examples were also provided (e.g., a strength: "I am highly committed to group work, actively participating," etc.; a weakness: "I tend to procrastinate, I am disorganized," etc.). It was emphasized that an effective group should leverage its members’ strengths and help them overcome their weaknesses.

This self-assessment and sharing exercise aim to encourage reflection on how these individual characteristics can be leveraged and strengthened in collaborative work, contributing to a more balanced and effective task distribution.

Finally, the formalization of the contract with the signatures of all group members plays both a symbolic and practical role, marking the individual and collective commitment to the group’s success. This practice enhances students’ sense of responsibility and motivates them to respect the contract and the agreed-upon rules. The signing of the document, created collectively, helps to strengthen trust among group members and consolidates the seriousness and importance of the activity.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the group contract in the Organizational Management course, as a support tool for the Team-Based Learning (TBL) methodology, contributes to fostering commitment and accountability among students. In the context of TBL, where active collaboration and shared responsibility are fundamental, the group contract plays an essential role by formalizing collaboration norms and clarifying each member’s expectations. This contributes to more effective communication, greater cohesion, and a more balanced task management within the group.

The practice of reviewing the contract during the semester allows students to adjust the defined norms and reflect on the group’s dynamics, enhancing the effectiveness of group work. As a support tool for TBL, the group contract proves to be not only an organizational resource but also a pedagogical framework that encourages the development of interpersonal skills essential for entering the job market.

In summary, the group contract complements the TBL methodology by providing a solid foundation for group work and helping to maintain students' focus and commitment throughout the semester. This study underscores the importance of integrating support tools, highlighting the group contract as an effective resource for promoting academic success in active learning environments.

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